

The Impacts of Religion and Social Media to National Integration and Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to examine and discuss the impacts of religion and social media to national integration and development in Nigeria. Since after the independent of Nigeria in 1960, national integration has been a national discussion and a difficult task to achieve till date due to the ethnic and religious crisis in the country. Ethno-religious and political crises in Nigeria are threatening the very survival of the country as a nation and made national integration impossible. In the twenty-first century where, social media became an instrument and easy way of sharing good and bad news contributed to both religious and political instability in the country. These crises have affected the integration, development, socioeconomic growth and political stability of Nigeria. As a result, many lives and properties were destroyed. However, the need for national integration is a necessity to all citizens and not a matter of choice. Therefore, against the above highlighted problems that this study examined and discussed the impact of religion and social media in bringing national integration and development in Nigeria. The findings of the study reveal that there has been ethnic and religious crisis in the Nigeria since its inception as an independent nation. It submits that religion and social media have an important role to play for the need to arrive on a proffer lasting solution for national unity and stability. The study recommends that the subject of national integration should not be neglected, rather it should be encouraged, affirmed, embraced and practiced among citizens of the country. The study employed a survey research method where people are randomly sampled as respondents, using questionnaire and physical interview as its means of data collection, and other manuscripts were also consulted.

Keywords: Religion, National Integration, Social-media, Crises, Development, Nigeria

Introduction

Nigeria is multi-ethnic, religious, cultural and linguistic diverse nation where national integration isn't a minor task to achieve. Since the amalgamation of the different groups that make up the entity now known as Nigeria, the country has remains in dire need for national integration.¹ Efforts have been put in place to integrate the country through constitutional means and adoption of various policies such as creation of states, but these efforts have not really produced the desired effect on the unity and stability of the country². As a single political entity, Nigeria came into existence on January 1st, 1914 when the colonialist amalgamated the existing Northern and Southern protectorates.³

Historically, Nigeria in pre-colonial days was generally referred to one of the countries in Western Sudan, and this reference was adopted by the early Arab writers like Al-Bakari, Ibn Khaldun, Attimbukti and As-Sa'adi.⁴ Nigeria became an independent nation in 1960 with the hope that Nigerian citizens will be integrated and tolerating one another for the purposes of peaceful-coexistence, good administration and development of the nation. Perhaps, as an independent nation, Nigeria still recounting and experiencing one conflict or the other and these conflicts constructed from differences in religious and ethnic identities which often result in destructive

violence.⁵ These crises have negatively impacted to national integration, development, stability and the security of the country due to the widespread and persistent of their nature.⁶

No doubt, it is the colonialist and their capitalist ideological underpinnings and the transplanting of the same character saw the seed of these crisis in Nigeria. The malicious ethnic structures and sectional initially created by colonial masters has brought about continuous and contending ethnic and religious crisis as well as impossibility of achieving national integration in the Nigerian society till date. Thus, the new trend of criminality and security lapses of the country in most Northern states during Jonathan and Buhari's administration is an ethnic, religious, political, sectional, tribal sentiments and hostilities among the citizens, and this kind of mindset have become dangerous signal that threaten the peaceful co-existence in Nigerian society.⁷

The struggle of human beings against one another has a variety of reasons. These reasons include religious disagreements that involves differences based on interpretations of religious doctrine and practice, tribalism and sectional sentiments and a tendency towards violent confrontation⁸. For example, the struggles between the Catholic and Orthodox churches, or the wars associated with the Protestant Reformation and Counter Reformation; also, the violence and disagreement seen between Sunni and Shi'ah Muslims is also in this category. The conflict arises when religious fundamentalists see their coreligionists as being insufficiently pious, not knowing that only God knew those who are pious among His creatures. Another form of religious violence is between completely different religions, in other word inter-religious violence.⁹ For example, wars between Muslims and Christians or Hindus and Buddhists have been framed as wars for the benefit or detriment of particular religions, although some religions are fighting over doctrinal differences, and most conflict stems from secular causes such as a desire for political power, a struggle for resources, ethnic rivalries, economic competition and religious communities.¹⁰

Conceptual Clarification

Religion: The word "religion" in Arabic الدين has been variously defined by scholars of different fields and these definitions provide different meaning for the term religion, and other definitions make an attempt in providing a specific or a single description of the word religion for a similar meaning, but this attempt was rejected and criticized by other scholars such as Ernst Feil, he argued that religion does not have a universal meaning. Religion in view of other scholars is a set of beliefs, feelings, practices, dogmas and practices that define the relations between human being and sacred or divinity¹¹. According to Olabimtan,¹² religion is also being defined by a specific element or its symbol such as dogmas, sacred things, and symbols; and religion also seen as a belief in spiritual beings.

Religion etymologically comes from the Latin words *Ligare* (to bind), *relegere* "to unite or link" and "relationship." Thus, the etymology of the word "Religion" from the above meanings shows that it is essentially a relationship, a link established between human and divine deity. It is something that links or unites man with transcendent being that he believed to exist and deserve to be worship. Religion has been constructed to be a fixed relationship between man and some non-human entity, the sacred, the supernatural being and or the self-existence. Religion is best described as man's awareness of the existence of a supernatural being whom he believes to be his creator and controller of the entire universe, and the concept of religion is anchored in the idea of belief and the fear of God, since religion makes sincerity, contentment and selfless services.¹³

Social Media Platform: Social media platforms are computer-based technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through virtual networks. It is an Internet based electronic that gives users quick communication, such as personal information, documents, videos, and photos. Users engage with social media via a computer, tablet, or smartphone via web-based software or applications. Social media originated as a means to interact with friends and family, but was later adopted for businesses in order to take advantage of a popular new communication methodology to reach out customers. The power of social media is the ability to connect and share information with anyone on Earth, in other word, sharing and receiving information with many people simultaneously.¹⁴ In 21st century, social media became the fastest way of sharing good and bad news due to the

rapid of its development. This rapid development of media platforms in the contemporary world creates an opportunity for people to share their experiences and views that are not verified by any legal institution in Nigeria. As a result, hate and violence speech has become more hazardous than carrying arms and perpetrating violent activities in the society.¹⁵

The table below shows the top ten social media platforms in the year 2022. The table also indicate the founder(s) of that media, year of launching and the total number of users as at 2nd November, 2022.

2022 Top Ten (10) Social Media Platforms by Monthly Active Users.

S/N	NAME	FOUNDER(S)	LAUNCHED	USERS
1	Facebook	Mark Zuckerberg, Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum	2004	2.9 billion
2	YouTube	Jawed Karim, Steve Chen, Chad Hurley.	2005	2.2 billion
3	WhatsApp	Brian Acton, Jan Koum	2009	2 billion
4	Instagram	Kevin Systrom, Mike Krieger	2010	2 billion
5	WeChat	Allen Zhang	2011	1.3 billion
6	TikTok	Byte Dance Ltd, Zhang Yiming	2016	1 billion
7	Messenger	Kavin Bharti Mittal	2011	976 million
8	Telegram	Pavel Durov, Nikolai Durov	2013	700 million
9	Douyin	Zhang Yiming	2016	613 million
10	Snapchat	Evan Spiegel, Bobby Murphy	2011	538 million

Source: SEJ, Search Engine Journal Online.¹⁶

National Integration

National integration and peaceful coexistence of multi-cultural and multi-religious nation (Nigeria) has been a national discourse in the country since it secured independence in 1960. Despite global states’ adoption of the constitutional principle of unity within diversity among nations, national integration remains a major challenge to most nations, including Nigeria. The state of national integration in Nigeria has been under the persistent negative influence of insecurity, poverty, deprivation, illiteracy, ignorance, corruption and poor leadership/governance. The concept of national integration is one of those elusive concepts in term of definition¹⁷. The literature on integration is replete with different definitions of the term.¹⁸ It is often not clear how the concept is to be interpreted because of its so many meanings and definition. Besides these diverse connotations, the term is used interchangeably with nation-building, national development, political development, unity, stability and socioeconomic growth¹⁹. The term integration is defined as “A *relationship of community among people within the same political entity, and a state of mind or disposition to be cohesive to act together to be committed to mutual programs.*”²⁰

From the above definition, it is observed that there is lack of relationship among Nigerian citizens. In fact, there is lack of common commitment to mutual programs in promoting national integration in the country. According to Haas²¹ he defined integration as the process whereby political actors in several distinct national settings are persuaded to shift their loyalties, expectations and political activities to a new center whose institutions processes demand jurisdiction over the pre-existing national states. Similar definition is given by Lindberg²² as he views integration as a process whereby nations forgo the desire and ability to conduct foreign and key domestic policies independently of each other, seeking instead to make joint decisions or to delegate the decision-making process to new central organs. According to Agbodike,²³ he sees national integration as a process leading to political cohesion and sentiments of loyalty towards a central political authority and institutions by individuals belonging to different social groups or political units. It is possible to define national integration

as the progressive reduction of cultural and regional tensions and discontinuities in the process of creating political and religious intolerance in the community.

National Development: National development can be seen as the overall success of a nation. It is also a collective socio-economic, political stability and religious advancement of a country. It refers to a phenomenon that embraces a whole nation. This is best achieved through development planning, which can be described as the country's collection of strategies mapped out by the government.²⁴

Colonial Masters and National Integration in Nigeria

The colonial masters made frantic efforts to unite Nigeria in one way or the other, and at the same time created division and feelings of hatred between the North and the South²⁵. It is possible to say that colonialists have sown the seed of disuniting the country in the name of providing unity, stability and national integration. Up to the present time, Nigeria is still in search of unity among its people. Consequently, Nigerians lack common vision and sense of national integration and a sense of common citizenship. For over sixty-three years of the flag of independence, the country still has often pulled down by joint identity and integration crisis²⁶. Cultivation of national outlook has inadvertently given way to a continued selfish attitude to nation-building by the frustrated nations whose emotions are stirred by the clandestine tribal organizations coordinating the races in the hot race for relevance within the polity, these clandestine organizations later metamorphosed into political parties when party politics was introduced in the country by the colonial masters.²⁷ It is possible to disclose that this political party creation creates an impact in the life of Nigerians negatively where tolerance, integration and development of the country becomes impossible because of the political arrangement by British colonists.²⁸ As a result of these political parties creation, the level of intolerance among the citizens of Nigeria becoming a higher greater every day and this has led to the loss of lives, and properties worth millions in the country.

Efforts for National Integration in Nigeria

Nigeria as a product of British experiment in political cloning, is a politically arranged country.²⁹ It consists of different ethnic groups, religious diversity and political godfathers who are supposed to be in the front to unite the country, but unfortunately standing on their heterogeneous in many respects which continues to be in promoting national disintegration among the citizens.³⁰ Now the question is, how have these ethnic groups cooperate to achieve national integration and how have those in power work together to achieve national integration and unity among the disparate groups that make up Nigeria towards the common goal of integration, peace and unity? To answer the above question, one could say that various policies have been put in place such as state creation, federal character and quota system for national unity. Nevertheless, the political history of Nigeria has been dominated by efforts of fashioning the system sown by the colonialist.³¹ Thus, to suit the people who are diverse in so many areas including religion, socio-political and economic formations, administrative styles, social norms and personality, historical evolution, disproportionate population, unequal economic resources and educational attainments, as well as differences in social wants, preferences, talents and opportunities.³² These diversities generate mutual suspicion and misunderstanding in Nigeria that keep people separated. According to Ogugua,³³ he argues that *none of the colonialist truly loved Nigeria and Nigerians, but they were concerned with building both political and financial empires to enhance the spirit of regionalism and ethnicity among the citizens in the country.*³⁴ Based on these references, one can say that the political elites in Nigeria maintained the structure of European Colonialist by engaging themselves in the pursuit of ease life, amassing of wealth and personal development along ethnic lines.³⁵

Consequent upon the above, the initial effort towards unity and national integration resulted in the state creation. According to Ayoade,³⁶ the attempt to redress North and South regional imbalance resulted in the creation of additional states in the country. He further said that the state creation could not solve the problem of national unity in Nigeria rather increasing signs of disunity in the country. To solve the problems of domination and marginalization and to ensure the structural balance of claims and gains by various groups and interests in

Nigeria, the federal character principle was conceived. The term was coined by the Constitution Drafting Committee that drafted the 1979 constitution. The federal character principle was enshrined in section 14(3) of the 1979 and 1999 constitutions respectively. Hence, section 14(3) of the 1999 constitution as amended states that:

The composition of the Government of the Federation or any of its agencies and the conduct of its affairs shall be carried out in such a manner as to reflect the federal character of Nigeria and the need to promote national unity and also to command national loyalty, thereby ensuring that there shall be no predominance of persons from a few states or from a few ethnic or other sectional groups in that Government or any of its agencies.

From the above constitutional statement, you can see that the only reason of federal character in Nigeria is to ensure harmony, promoting national integration and stability of the nation. It emphasizes on the need for ethnic and religion balancing as a necessity in the evolution of Nigerian citizenship. The federal character principle may be used to satisfy the quest for representativeness and proportionality in allocating resources and in appointments, but in the application of this formula choices are made on the basis of criterion other than merit which leads to lowering of standard against national interest³⁷. Nevertheless, the major political parties of recent time in Nigeria have adopted the idea of federal character and have incorporated it in their party constitutions. But unfortunately, regional sentiment and selfish interests of the party leaders have in most cases rendered their constitutions impotent thereby frustrating the idea of rotational presidency.

Factors Responsible for the Lack of National Integration in Nigeria

The root causes for the lack of national integration in Nigeria is attributed to colonialist who saw the seed of tribalism and regional sentiments in the hearts of Nigerians³⁸. Based on the discussion in the preceding pages, the following were outlined as the major causes for the lack of national integration in Nigeria: Religious and Political intolerance, tribalism and corruption, poverty and unemployment, ignorance and sentiment, lack of religious orientation, fear of domination, hate speech on media platforms, religious preaching methods, election procedures and, government involvement in religious matters.

Data Presentation and Analysis on the Impact of Religion and Social-Media on National Integration and Development in Nigeria

Data for this research work were collected through questionnaire, interview and other sources. The following tables presented the information collected by the researchers in the field work from sixty-three (63) respondents in twenty-five (25) states of the federation. These states are: Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Borno, Bauchi, Benue, Delta, Enugu, Ebonyi, Ekiti, Gombe, Jigawa, Kano, Kwara, Kaduna, Katsina, Kogi, Nasarawa, Niger, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe and FCT respectively.

Table 1: Religion is a platform for peace and harmony where national integration can be promoted.

S/N	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	(a) Strongly Agree	49	77.8
2	(b) Agree	13	20.6
3	(c) Strongly Disagree	0	0
4	(d) Disagree	1	1.6
	Total	63	100

Interpretation of Data

The above table shows that majority of respondents representing 77.8% strongly agreed and 20.6% agreed that religion is a platform of peace and harmony where national integration can be promoted, due to the fact that majority of Nigerian citizens were the adherents of Islam and Christianity. So, when they are united and

accommodating one another, there would be strong integration and development in the country. Respondents representing 0% strongly disagree while 1.6% disagree respectively.

Table 2: National integration be achieved in Nigeria through religious orientation.

S/N	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	(a) Strongly Agree	34	54
2	(b) Agree	25	39.7
3	(c) Strongly Disagree	3	4.8
4	(d) Disagree	1	1.6
	Total	63	100

Interpretation of Data

Table two above shows that majority of respondents representing 54% strongly agree and 39.7% agree that national integration is possible to be achieved in Nigeria through religious orientation programs. Respondents representing 4.8% strongly disagree and respondents representing 1.6% disagree respectively.

Table 3: Lack of national integration is a threat to economic and social development in Nigeria.

S/N	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	(a) Strongly Agree	32	50.8
2	(b) Agree	26	41.3
3	(c) Strongly Disagree	2	3.2
4	(d) Disagree	3	4.8
	Total	63	100

Interpretation of Data

The above table shows that majority of respondents representing 50.8% strongly agree that lacks of national integration is a major problem threatening the unity, stability and economic development in Nigeria, also respondents representing 41.3% agree that absence of national integration is threat to national economic growth and social stability in Nigeria. Respondents representing 3.2% strongly disagree while 4.7% respondents disagree, they have views that lack of national integration is not a threat to economic and social development.

Table 4: Rapid development of media platforms affected the national integration in Nigeria

S/N	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	(a) Strongly Agree	31	49.2
2	(b) Agree	18	28.6
3	(c) Strongly Disagree	4	6.3
4	(d) Disagree	10	15.9
	Total	63	100

Interpretation of Data

Table four shows that the majority of respondents representing 49.2% strongly agree that rapid development of social media platforms that allow people to share their views without any legal measure have negativity affected

the level of integration in Nigeria, and 28.6% respondents agree upon respectively. But 6.3% respondents strongly disagree while 15.9% disagree respectively.

Table 5: Majority users of social media platforms are unaware of the implication of sharing hate and violence speech on national integration.

S/N	OPTIONS	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	(a) Strongly Agree	32	50.8
2	(b) Agree	19	30.2
3	(c) Strongly Disagree	3	4.8
4	(d) Disagree	9	14.3
	Total	63	100

Interpretation of Data

In the above table 5, majority of the respondents representing 50.8% strongly agree that the many users of social media platforms are not aware or lacks knowledge about the implications of sharing hate and violence speech on media, and respondents representing 30.2% also agree upon. Respondents representing 4.7% are strongly disagree while 14.3% respondents disagree respectively.

Discussion of Findings

From the findings of the research, it is established that lacks of national integration is one of the major problems affecting Nigeria since when it became an independence nation in 1960 from the British colonists. In line with the interpretation of data collected for this research, religion is a platform of peace, unity and stability where national integration should be promoted. Thus, religion have a significant role in promoting unity among citizens of the country through religious orientation programs targeting the adherents of the two major religions in Nigeria (Islam and Christianity). Some of the factors influencing the lack of national integration in the Nigeria include religious and political intolerance, poverty and unemployment, ignorance and selfishness, fear of domination, preaching methodology, election procedure etc. The rapid development of social media platforms contributed immensely to the growth of disintegration of Nigeria and Nigerian citizens; this is because violence and hate speeches are growing every single hour on social media. This happen to be the reason why Nigeria is yet to actualize and realize its dreams on national integration among it's citizens.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined and discussed the impact of religion and social media in bringing national integration and development in Nigeria. The findings of the study reveal that there has been an ethnic and religious crisis in the country since its inception as an independent nation in 1960. Despite these crisis, religion and social media have an important role to play for the need to arrive on a proffer lasting solution. Thus, the study submit that religious orientation programs and the proffer use of social media platforms are the way out in achieving national integration and development in Nigeria. The study made the following recommendations. The subject of national integration should not be neglected, rather it should be encouraged, affirmed, embraced and practiced by citizens in Nigeria for national development. Federal government should create a national ministry of religious affairs with different departments, such as dialogue and orientation, integration and development, quality, policy and strategy etc. Nigerian government should create a legal body that will take charge in regulating hate and violence speech on social media. Users of social media platforms should always be careful, focus and sincere of whatever information before posting on network. Religious leaders and scholars in different faith should work in synergy towards achieving national integration in Nigeria through religious orientation programs and other means.

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